

Product Recommendation Using Collaborative Filtering by Consumer Rating

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Abstract— The recommendation system of the website can not only recommend products for users and save users the time spent searching for products, but also help practitioners reduce unnecessary sales activities and management expenses. This study proposes a cooperative filtering algorithm based on user ratings by evaluating and extracting the ratings for the product given by user. Based on product ratings, the collaborative filtering algorithm is used to recommend potential products of interest to new users, and improve the accuracy of the services and sales of the website.

Keywords—Recommendation algorithm; Collaborative filtering; Rating

I. INTRODUCTION

Recommendation systems are used by E-commerce web sites to signify products to their customers. The products may be suggested based at the top general sellers on a site, based on the demographics of the customer, or based on an evaluation of the past shopping behavior of the customer as a prediction for future shopping behavior. Collaborative filtering is the process of comparing or filtering items using the perspectives of various people. Utilizing profiles allows for the completion of this filtering. In collaborative filtering strategies, profiles are found and acquired, and relationships between different records are determined using similarity models. User preferences, user behaviour patterns, or item properties are some possible categories for the data in the profiles.

Customers now have access to a wide variety of goods thanks to the e-commerce sector's exponential growth. Modern department stores with a huge selection of goods are e-commerce websites. Systems that make recommendations act as salespeople who can assess customers' needs and make product recommendations to them. Nearly all e-commerce websites in use today employ recommender systems to give users better user experiences by making suggestions they might find useful. It is simple to record different user feedbacks and activity. Different recommendation algorithms, including content-based, collaborative filtering, matrix factorization, and domain-specific systems like case-based, contextual recommender systems, have been developed in recent years. Also used to improve social networking services are location-based systems. In my study, I make use of collaborative filtering. This paper proposes an unplanned rating-based recommendation system that generates recommendations using product ratings as user feedback. The premise of

collaborative filtering algorithms is that items will be rated similarly by people with similar tastes.

It is designed on business environment. Based on product popularity, businesses may target potential consumers with the best-selling items on their websites. Additionally, cold-starting recommendation engines is a great application of this strategy. Here, a model-based collaborative filtering approach is discussed because it makes by-product predictions for a specific person by spotting trends based on potential outcomes from data from multiple users. Give customers product recommendations based on their past purchases and the reviews left by other users who bought similar products. When new visitors to the e-commerce site without any prior purchase history arrive for the first time, the most popular items offered on the business' website are recommended to them. Following a purchase, the recommendation system updates and offers recommendations for additional products based on the customer's past purchases and the reviews left by other website users. Collaborative filtering methods are used to complete the process.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Different methods are used in Recommendation systems. Types of Recommended systems are Collaborative filtering, Content-based filtering, Hybrid recommendation system etc... are used.

Zahid et. al. [5] For the unidentified or novel product, a forecast is generated based on the computed similarity. Despite having comparable calculation methods to the Pearson correlation measure, Jaccard, Mean Square Difference, Cosine, etc., triangle similarity has the drawback of only taking into account users' usual circumstances.

Rahul Kumar et. al. [3] The majority of e-commerce websites currently collect additional helpful input, such as reviews and reviews' helpfulness, to enhance the functionality of recommendation algorithms that employ user reviews. The tests are conducted using the product ratings and reviews from Amazon as the data source.

S. Ramachandram et. al. [1] The performance of the collaborative filtering recommendation system is assessed in this research, along with the difficulties faced by the system. Along with the applications of the collaborative filtering recommendation system, other types of rank that can be re-collected from the stoner to evaluate items are also discussed.

Xiaoyong Li et. al. [2] Although collaborative filtering is one of the most widely used methods in e-commerce, there are still some issues with it, including "cold start" and "data sparse." In the paper, we propose a novel method that combines the clustering algorithm with the SVD algorithm, which is broadly used in the field of image-processing, into a collaborative filtering algorithm in response to a number of issues, such as "data sparse" and bad "real-time" produced by a large number of registering users. Our tests demonstrate that the method not only solves the "cold start" and "data sparse" issues, but also boosts a system's effectiveness and scalability.

Cong Li [4] In this work, the ECRec collaborative filtering-based E-commerce recommender system is put out. ECRec is created and discovered at the Client/Server architecture, with 4 defining modules (RecDB, RecEngine, Configuration Console and Monitor Agnet). Additionally, ECRec uses four advanced CF algorithms in addition to four simple CF methods for various applications.

METHODOLOGY

In order to provide pertinent product suggestions across digital domains, collaborative filtering is a form of personalised recommendation approach that analyses user commonalities (based on site interactions).

COLLABORATIVE FILTERING

One of the most well-known similarity metrics for collaborative filtering recommender systems is the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC), which is used to determine how closely consumers are connected. Although correlation-based prediction techniques have been shown to work effectively, they have several drawbacks.

$$r = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

It uses rating_beauty dataset is taken through a public data-gathering platform called Kaggle, which consists of 4 columns and more than 1000 rows. The dataset used is in Comma Separated Values (csv) format. The dataset is

analyzed with the help of pandas, NumPy, matplotlib and sklearn.

III. BUILD MODEL

The primary stage in product recommendation is model building. Collaborative filtering is used by the customer when developing the model.

At step 1 the numpy, pandas, matplotlib, sklearn libraries are imported and csv file are imported.

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# %matplotlib inline
plt.style.use("ggplot")

import sklearn
from sklearn.decomposition import TruncatedSVD
```

```
amazon_ratings = pd.read_csv('ratings_Beauty.csv')
amazon_ratings = amazon_ratings.dropna()
amazon_ratings.head()
```

Then dataset is passed through a shape() attribute of panda library to obtain the shape of data frame. The datas are displayed in an order as from the product with the most rating to the product with the least rating and it is done by using groupby to group two categories and sort of to list the ratings from the most rated to the least.

```
amazon_ratings.shape
```

```
popular_products = pd.DataFrame(amazon_ratings.groupby('ProductId')['Rating'].count())
most_popular = popular_products.sort_values("Rating", ascending=False)
most_popular.head(10)
```

Later top 30 dataset is plotted in a bar graph using the plot () class in the matplotlib library.

```
most_popular.head(30).plot(kind = "bar")
```

<AxesSubplot: xlabel='ProductId' >

TruncatedSVD function and stored in variable SVD which is then set to fit_transform function of python which is used on the training data so that we can scale the training data and also learn the scaling parameters.

```
SVD = TruncatedSVD(n_components=10)
decomposed_matrix = SVD.fit_transform(X)
decomposed_matrix.shape
```

IV. RESULT

The resulted data is then put into the `corrcoef()` function of the numpy library, to obtain the correlation matrix.

```
correlation_matrix = np.corrcoef(decomposed_matrix)
correlation_matrix.shape
```

Lastly, the list of data is printed which recommends the 10 most popular products by listing the value where `product_id > 0.90`.

```
Recommend = list(X.index[correlation_product_ID > 0.90])
# Removes the item already bought by the customer
Recommend.remove(i)
Recommend[0:9]

['1304139212',
 '130414643X',
 '1304174867',
 '1304174905',
 '1304511111',
 '1304511154',
 '1304622452',
 '1304622657',
 '1304622665']
```

CONCLUSION

Making recommendation systems has extensively used collaborative filtering created on user referrals. Collaborative filtering, which is founded on filtering Products Id, is employed in this study. To develop a recommendation system, other users can refer to user reviews for certain Products. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient approach is used to determine how similar two users are to one another. For collaborative filtering recommender systems, it is the most often used similarity metric to determine how closely two users are linked. The rating is calculated by multiplying the user's rank by the Pearson similarity value once each user's similarity value has been determined. Then the number of similarities is divided to obtain the best product suggestions.

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